

Pragmatic Analysis of Deception and Miscommunication in Saki's 'The Open Window'

Dr. Nagamurali Eragamreddy

English Language Unit, Preparatory Studies Centre, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Salalah, Sultanate of Oman.

ABSTRACT: This research looks at how Saki, also known as H.H. Munro, uses Grice's maxims to accomplish practical consequences in his short story "The Open Window." The research investigates how meaning is created through speech and how violations of these principles lead to misconceptions using a pragmatic approach. The research examines how the story's characters interact in accordance with or without respect to Grice's four maxims—quality, quantity, manner, and relation—using a qualitative descriptive technique. The study's questions explore Vera's application of these aphorisms, the irony and misinterpretation resulting from Framton Nuttel's presumptions regarding them, Munro's potential social critique of Victorian communication conventions, and the narrative's thematic implications of deception, manipulation, and social anxiety. Thirty of Grice's maxims are found in the story, which Vera disobeys to produce hilarious consequences. The conversation sheds light on how these broken rules lead to misunderstandings and manipulation while also providing an understanding of the story's social setting and the intentions of the protagonists. This pragmatic approach highlights the significance of effective and transparent communication in interpersonal relationships while enhancing our comprehension of the story's dynamics, comedy, and thematic depth.

KEYWORDS: Grice's maxims, pragmatic analysis, communication, humor

INTRODUCTION

Background

One of the greatest authors of the Edwardian era is H.H. Munro (Saki). He has a profound understanding of human nature and the current societal challenges of his era. Saki's brief narratives portray the sense of impending disaster frightening Britain on the brink of a global catastrophe while also revealing his sardonic attitude toward numerous facets of Edwardian social life. Saki achieved success in a variety of genres, although Russian readers are most familiar with him as a short story writer. The collections "Reginald" (1904) and "The Chronicles of Clovis" (1912), which demonstrated Munro's mastery of the short story form, are among his most well-known works (Fonseka, 2015). Although a promising literary career was tragically cut short by his death in World War I, his work is still acclaimed for its ageless themes, social critique, and cutting humor (Saki, 2017). An iconic short tale by H.H. Munro is "The Open Window," which was first published in 1914 as a part of the collection "Beasts and Super-Beasts" (Munro, 1914). The protagonist of the story is Framton Nuttel, an anxious guy in search of a tranquil rural getaway to help him cope with his anxiety (Munro, 1914). But when he meets Vera, Mrs. Sappleton's little niece, his visit to her house takes an unexpected turn.

A great storyteller with a taste for mischief, Vera (Munro, 1914) spins a spectacular narrative about a recent tragedy involving the brothers and husband of Mrs. Sappleton, who purportedly vanished while out hunting on the moors. Because of his anxious state and gullibility, Nuttel is easily surprised and quickly accepts Vera's complex deception (Munro, 1914). The plot revolves around Vera's deft use of words and deliberate disregard for Grice's conversational rules (Fonseka, 2015). Framton's misreadings and his more agitated actions as he sees the putative tragedy playing out in front of him are what make the situation humorous (Munro, 1914). "The Open Window" exemplifies Saki's skill with the short tale format. He conjures up a humorous situation that tackles issues of deceit, societal fears, and the power of narrative in a few pages (Fonseka, 2015). The story's insightful representation of human gullibility, surprising turns, and humorous dialogue are what have made it so famous for so long.

Overview of Grice's Theory of Conversational Implicature

Grice gives an explanation of the idea of conversational implicature in the form of a broad flow of ideas the speaker wants the listener to consider. In response, the hearer understands the implicature in light of the conversation's circumstances, including background information, and acknowledges the speaker's goal. When someone says something (p) in a way that suggests something else (q), they are establishing conversational implicatures. There are three primary phases in this process: 1) it is presumed that the

speaker abides by the cooperative principle or conversational maxims; 2) declaring p is consistent with the speaker's view that q is true; and 3) based on 2, the speaker presumes that the audience can infer that the speaker believes in q. According to Grice (1989), this comprehension depends on the listener's capacity to deduce the speaker's inferred meaning from their utterance. The letter p represents what was spoken in terms of conventional meaning, whereas the letter q represents what was intended in terms of implicit meaning. The speaker must think that q is correct as he is expected to follow the maxims or, at the absolute least, the Cooperative Principle. The rationale for this is that he is lying if he doesn't think that q, which goes against the first quality principle. Furthermore, since the speaker is abiding by the maxims and/or the Cooperative Principle, the speaker should express p with the hope that the hearer would comprehend that q is required. The foundation of an implicature's effectiveness is the idea that both parties have a common understanding pertinent to the nature and goal of the discourse. The implicature cannot be correctly performed if it is absent. According to Levinson (1983), shared understanding is attained when the speaker's (or "sender's") purpose is understood by both parties. Put another way, a conversational implicature—and interaction overall—succeeds when the listener appropriately understands the speaker's goal (Lalić, 2020).

Purpose

The purpose of this research is to examine how H.H. Munro achieves pragmatic effects in his short tale "The Open Window" by utilizing Grice's maxims of discourse. The study will examine how meaning is created via speech and how misconceptions result from pragmatic breaches by examining how characters follow or disregard these maxims.

Research Questions

1. What is the way that Vera employs Grice's four maxims—quantity, quality, relation, and manner—in her interactions with Framton Nuttel?
2. How does the hilarity and misinterpretation in the narrative stem from Nuttel's readings of Vera's communication based on his presumptions about the maxims?
3. Does Munro make any implicit social commentary regarding Victorian communication patterns or social conventions through the usage of Grice's maxims?
4. How can a fuller comprehension of the themes of deceit, manipulation, and social anxiety in "The Open Window" result from an examination of Grice's maxims?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Types of Maxims

Maxim of Quantity: According to this maxim, one should only provide as much information as is essential without going overboard (Grice, 1975).

Maxim of Quality: Sincerity is emphasized in this maxim. According to Grice (1975), speakers should only discuss topics for which they have sufficient evidence and refrain from stating anything they perceive to be untrue or misleading.

Maxim of Manner: This maxim emphasizes expression that is clear and well-organized. It is best to stay away from vagueness, ambiguity, and needless prolixity (being unduly wordy) (Grice, 1975; Eragamreddy, 2022).

Maxim of Relation: This maxim emphasizes applicability. People ought to stay on topic and refrain from bringing up other subjects (Grice, 1975; Eragamreddy, 2022).

Previous Research on Grice's Maxims

Hossain's (2021) study offers a thorough analysis of Grice's maxims and how they apply to regular communication. The study emphasizes how crucial Grice's cooperative principle is to building effective communication and preserving wholesome interpersonal and professional connections. People may make sure that their contributions to a discussion are genuine, relevant, illuminating, and unambiguous by following the four maxims of quantity, quality, relationship, and manner. The idea of conversational implicature—in which speakers communicate meaning beyond the literal understanding of their words—is also covered in Hossain's assessment. This part of Grice's theory emphasizes how inferential reasoning plays a crucial role in deciphering implicit information and how intricate human communication is. The examination underscores the applicability of Grice's maxims in promoting meaningful and successful communication across a range of circumstances.

A thorough summary of Paul Grice's seminal theory of conversation, as presented in his William James Lectures, can be found in Wilson and Sperber (2022). They draw attention to the long-lasting influence of Grice's work on contemporary pragmatics theories, highlighting the idea that dialogue is a joint effort governed by the principles of veracity, relevance, informativeness, and style. The writers talk about how implicatures are understood, how explicit meaning differs from implicit meaning, and how implicatures are categorized into many kinds. All of these topics are influenced by Grice's framework. Furthermore, they point out that although there have been suggestions to add to or alter Grice's framework, his lectures continue to constitute a fundamental component of pragmatic analysis. The assessment by Wilson and Sperber emphasizes how Grice's theory laid the groundwork for later ideas of pragmatic analysis and speech interpretation.

The contribution of Grice's maxims to the cooperative and mutually understood character of communication is thoroughly examined by Abba et al. (2022). The writers stress how crucial it is to follow Grice's Cooperative Principle to minimize uncertainty in dialogue. They clarify that to guarantee successful and transparent communication, speakers need to adhere to Grice's four maxims: quantity, quality, relation, and manner. The authors do point out that presenters may purposefully disregard these guidelines by leaving out portions of their remarks, which results in a non-observance of the guidelines. Because of this purposeful omission, the listener may have to infer the intended meaning, which might lead to misinterpretations or different interpretations of the message. To create meaningful discussions, Abba et al. stress the importance of cooperation between speakers and listeners as well as the importance of pragmatics in comprehending language usage within a community. They conclude that Grice's maxims are still essential to the study of pragmatics and are necessary to comprehend communication meaning.

Yuldasheva (2024) explores how Grice's maxims served as a cornerstone for the study of implicature and speaker meaning in pragmatics. The study emphasizes how these four maxims—Quantity, Quality, Relation, and Manner—provide recommendations for effective communication by highlighting the significance of veracity, informativeness, relevance, and clarity in speech. Nonetheless, Yuldasheva also notes that there are cultural variations that may impact how the Gricean Maxims are interpreted and put into practice, highlighting the difficulties of applying them globally. The study's overall findings indicate that while the Gricean Maxims offer insightful guidance on successful communication, their implementation might differ depending on the culture and situation, necessitating careful consideration and modification.

Studies on The Open Window

A detailed examination of H.H. Munro's "The Open Window," with an emphasis on its themes, characters, and narrative devices, is given by Singh's (2022) research. The research makes use of several analytical techniques, such as literary theory, to reveal the subtleties and underlying meaning of the narrative. The study emphasizes Saki's sardonic and sarcastic storytelling style, which is essential to the plot's progression. Saki illustrates how looks may be deceitful by examining issues of deception and illusion via the figure of Framton Nuttel. Additionally, the research explores Saki's use of wit and humor, which draws readers in and gives the story depth. By breaking down the narrative, Yuldasheva reveals how Saki creates a story that is both thought-provoking and enjoyable, giving readers a complex grasp of societal norms and human nature.

The research by Maeedi and Jasim (2021) offers a stylistic interpretation of Saki's "The Open Window" via the Johnstone model. The study analyzes Johnstone's three persuasive strategies—quasi-logical, presentational, and analogical—to examine persuasion as a crucial tactic used by the story's central characters. The study looks at how these persuasive techniques are applied throughout the story using both qualitative and quantitative analysis. Maeedi and Jasim hope to clarify the language strategies employed by the characters to convince one another in the story's setting by utilizing Johnstone's model. The analysis's conclusions point to a tight connection between Johnstone's list of persuasive techniques and the story setting of "The Open Window." This research emphasizes the subtleties of persuasion as a literary device inside the narrative and advances our comprehension of Saki's storytelling skills.

The analysis of "The Open Window" by Fonseka (2015) explores the issues of deceit and social conventions that were common in Victorian and Edwardian culture. According to the research, Munro used Vera as a vehicle to illustrate the lack of regard for outsiders in that era's English culture, reflecting on his multicultural upbringing. Munro shows how readily people may become the target of jokes and mockery via deceit by manipulating Framton Nuttel, an innocent-seeming character. The study highlights Munro's ability to write a story that develops like a ghost story and captivates readers with its unexpected turns. Munro's narrative offers a critique

of societal standards and human conduct by depicting the English culture of the period as devoid of empathy and respect for foreigners. Fonseka's study enhances the comprehension of "The Open Window" by placing it in the larger context of deceit and society.

Relevance of Studying Grice's Maxims

A useful foundation for examining communication in literature is provided by Grice's Cooperative Principle and the maxims that go along with it (Yuldasheva, 2024). These adages set a standard for cooperative and transparent communication, but their real potency comes from the way writers intentionally employ them to achieve certain literary effects. We may learn more about the characters' motives and the text's underlying themes by analyzing how they follow or disregard the maxims. A character who consistently withholds information, for example, may be concealing a secret or controlling the discourse (Tannen et al., 2015). This is a violation of the maxim of quantity. Characters that violate the maxim of quality by using deceptive language may also be attempting to build dramatic tension or deceive (Putra et al., 2023). Grice's tenets are frequently broken by characters in writing to provide ambiguity, comedy, or suspense. For instance, characters may use remarks that appear absurd (breaking the relation maxim) to make others laugh at their misinterpretations (Rahmi et al., 2018). Similarly, characters that break the rule of quantity by speaking subtly through silence or unspoken communication can evoke mystery and encourage readers to actively participate in deciphering meaning (Andy & Ambalegin, 2019).

Examining the Power Dynamics and Social Context: Grice's maxims may also be applied to investigate the social context and power dynamics in a piece of literature. Depending on their social status, cultural background, or connection with the addressee, characters may deliberately decide to follow or disregard the maxims (Dewi, 2023). For example, in a society that values politeness, a character who adheres to the maxim of manners and talks frankly and immediately could be perceived as forceful, or even harsh. Studying Grice's maxims therefore provides us with the necessary skills to examine the subtleties of communication found in literary writings. We may learn a lot about the work's social environment, reader engagement, character motives, and thematic significance by analyzing how characters follow or disregard these maxims. A deeper and more complex understanding of how writers use language to produce meaning and consequences is made possible by this paradigm.

METHODOLOGY

This study was presented in words, phrases, and paragraphs using descriptive language. As a result, the descriptive qualitative approach was used in this investigation. Since the qualitative descriptive technique is not aligned with any specific theoretical orientation, it is the least advanced approach in terms of epistemological attitude. Don't assume it's easy, though, simply because it's the least conceptually complex and general! A good study, however, conceals the thought and preparation that go into gathering data, analyzing it, and presenting the results (Stanley, 2014). In terms of data collection methodology, this study used non-participatory techniques and the observational approach Lavia et al., (2018). Additionally, a pragmatic approach to data analysis was used in this study, and the pragmatic identification technique was applied. The pragmatic competence in-equalizing method was used to analyze the data. This method was employed since the researcher balanced the data elements using the applicable theory after the investigation. According to Sudaryanto (2015), pragmatic competence in equalizing is a method that contrasts all of the pertinent factors and data points. The initial stage involved gathering information by repeatedly reading and evaluating the short narrative. Subsequently, the investigator gathered information pertinent to the cooperation principle and maxims. Additionally, the context was taken into account while interpreting the data gathering, and the theory that was used was then equalized.

RESULTS

Thirty data points illustrating Grice's cooperative maxims were discovered in the short story "The Open Window." The following table displays the research's findings.

Table 1: Occurrence of Maxims in the short story, The Open Window

S. No	Maxim Type	Occurrence
1	Quality	12
2	Quantity	5
3	Manner	9
4	Relation	4
Total		30

DISCUSSION

Grice's cooperation principle's "Maxim of Quality" has to do with the speaker's veracity and correct information. Characters in the provided extracts express information about feelings, actions, and intentions; this information is taken to be true given the context. The young woman is direct in the conversation; her assertion regarding her aunt's impending visit, for instance, is taken at its value. In a similar vein, it is presumed that the caller told the truth when he said he knew Mrs. Sappleton, even if he didn't know for sure if she was married or not. The aunt's tragedy, as mentioned by the kid, and her belief in her husband and siblings' return are both depicted as real occurrences. Furthermore, it appears from Mrs. Sappleton's succinct statement that she was straightforward and honest when telling Mr. Framton Nuttel that her husband and brothers were coming from a shooting. Furthermore, Nuttel's disclosure to Mrs. Sappleton on his recommended rest and diet indicates his effort to provide her with truthful information regarding his health. Overall, because the characters' words are consistent with the honesty required in cooperative communication, these examples of the quality maxim add to the story's consistency and plausibility.

According to Grice's cooperative concept, the "Maxim of Quantity" indicates that speakers should impart just the right quantity of information—neither too little nor too much—for the situation. Characters in the provided passages only divulge information pertinent to the discussion; superfluous details are omitted. For instance, her remark on Nuttel's retreat implies that she is giving just enough context to express her worry about his seclusion without going into much detail. In a similar vein, Nuttel's comment about his familiarity with the locals suggests that he is giving the niece a direct response to her inquiry without going into needless detail. In addition, the niece's query regarding Nuttel's familiarity with the area and the young woman's question about his acquaintance with her aunt all call for precise, pertinent information, which Nuttel delivers in an easy-to-understand manner. This devotion to the quantity guideline keeps the discourse from getting too detailed or rambling and helps to keep it flowing. Furthermore, Nuttel gives Mrs. Sappleton just enough information about his medical regimen in his statement about his physicians' orders, without going into needless detail to make it difficult for her to grasp. All in all, these examples of the maxim of quantity support clear and efficient discussion by guaranteeing that the information is pertinent, succinct, and appropriate for the situation.

Grice's cooperation principle's "Maxim of Manner" advises speakers to communicate in an unambiguous, succinct, and ordered manner while minimizing obscurity and ambiguity. Characters in the above excerpts follow this rule by speaking understandable and direct way, which improves the efficacy of their interactions. The girl's direct and succinct comment on her aunt's impending visit sets the tone for more discussion with Mr. Nuttel. She also shows consideration and politeness by acknowledging that Mr. Nuttel has to put up with her presence until her aunt comes. Thus, the girl asks a straightforward inquiry that gets right to the point concerning Mr. Nuttel's knowledge of her aunt without sugarcoating it. In addition, Mr. Nuttel's reaction is succinct and direct, suggesting a lack of in-depth familiarity with the aunt. The caller is respectful of the listener's query when he is forthright and honest in his statement that he just knows Mrs. Sappleton's name and address. The caller's inquisitiveness about Mrs. Sappleton's past is evident in his internal monologue on her marital status.

Mrs. Sappleton makes a clear and instructive comment on the open window, outlining the rationale for its continued presence without needless detail. Her conversational tone and precise reference to her husband's and siblings' homecoming show that she has an orderly and transparent communication style. A dynamic tone is also added to the exchange by Mrs. Sappleton's obvious and impassioned expression of her delight upon seeing her husband and brothers at home. Her remark on their dirty look is direct and perceptive, demonstrating her attention to detail. Finally, Mr. Nuttel gives a succinct justification for his need for rest and removes any doubt with his declaration of his physicians' recommendations. It is simple and enlightening. Overall, the characters' devotion to the rule of manner improves the effectiveness and clarity of their communication, making sure that their words are comprehended clearly and without ambiguity.

According to Grice's cooperative concept, speakers should make their contributions pertinent to the current discussion, as suggested by the Maxim of Relation. Characters in the above excerpts follow this rule by keeping their speech relevant and making sure that it has anything to do with the subject at hand. The child's comment on the terrible event that occurred three years ago is relevant as it gives background knowledge regarding Mrs. Sappleton's past—a subject of debate at the moment. The youngster also establishes a connection between this catastrophe and the duration since the caller's sister's visit, placing the incident inside a context that the caller is familiar with. The context-relevant remark made by Mrs. Sappleton on the open window is that it clarifies the rationale behind keeping the window open, which was the subject of an earlier conversation. She also refers to her brothers' and husband's return from the shooting, making a connection between her remarks and their location and the present topic of discussion.

The caller's awareness of the surroundings is a topic of interest in their conversation, therefore the niece's inquiry regarding the local population is pertinent. Inquiring more into the caller's history and level of acquaintance with the location, her query also advances the conversation. Nuttel's inquiry on the tragedy is pertinent as it looks for further details and explanation regarding the subject the youngster brought up. His comment that catastrophes don't seem to belong in the lovely country setting also connects to the conversation's overarching subject, which is the rural retreat's serene environment. Thus, the characters' devotion to the relation maxim guarantees that their contributions are significant and advance the debate. They preserve coherence and clarity in their communication by remaining pertinent to the current subject, which makes it simpler for the listener to follow the discourse and comprehend the intended message.

Vera's Use of Grice's Maxims

Quality: By completely making up the narrative about the open window and the ghostly reappearance, Vera flagrantly transgresses this rule (violates).

Quantity: Vera seriously disregards this maxim. She creates an unnecessary narrative about spirits returning (flouts), going far beyond what is necessary to fully explain the terrible incident.

Manner: By employing dramatic descriptions and emotionally charged words (flouts), Vera flouts this maxim. Because she is so focused on producing a chilling impact, her voice gets muddled.

Relation: Vera seriously violates this rule by digressing into a lengthy digression on the purported tragedy, which has no bearing on the topic at hand (flouts).

Hilarity and Misinterpretation

Framton Nuttel's misinterpretations stem from his presumptions that Vera follows Grice's maxims, which give birth to comedy and misunderstanding. Because he thinks Vera and Mrs. Sappleton are telling the truth (qualities), he accepts the ghost story. Though she is fabricating a narrative, he thinks Vera is being relevant (relation) by giving the open window context. He sees her long narrative as a succinct and straightforward exposition (manner), without the theatrical flourishes.

Social Commentary on Victorian Communication

There's a chance that social criticism is implied. Indirect communication and civility were highly prized in Victorian culture. Perhaps Vera is making fun of this kind of obliqueness by spinning a fantastical tale rather than inquiring directly about Nuttel's well-being, which could be construed as unfriendly. Nuttel's literal reading may be seen as a criticism of those who overlook the underlying meaning and take excessively flowery words at their value.

Deceit, Manipulation, and Social Anxiety

Grice's maxims aid in the analysis of these ideas:

Deceit: By fabricating a story, Vera tricks Nuttel (violates quality). His idea that she follows the maxims serves as the foundation for her manipulation.

Manipulation: To fit her plot, Vera takes advantage of Nuttel's social nervousness and his longing for a tranquil retreat.

Social Anxiety: Nuttel's misunderstanding of social cues and over-sensitivity to possible hazards are the results of his social anxiety.

Ultimately, a closer look at Grice's maxims in "The Open Window" reveals more about the characters' communication preferences and the misunderstandings and laughter that result from them. Nuttel misinterprets Vera's obvious transgressions of the maxims, especially in Quality, Quantity, and Relation, in a humorous way. This highlights the difference between directness and indirectness and acts as a social criticism of Victorian communication conventions. Furthermore, the narrative exemplifies themes of lying, manipulation, and social anxiety, as Vera takes advantage of Framton's social discomfort to craft her intricate plot. In general, the utilization of Grice's maxims enhances comprehension of the narrative's dynamics and its depiction of interpersonal relationships.

CONCLUSION

Using Grice's cooperative principles as a lens, this pragmatic analysis of "The Open Window" shows how underlying social dynamics and humor can arise from communication failures. Vera seriously transgresses the principles of Relation (maintaining

relevance), Quality (truthfulness), Quantity (giving the appropriate quantity of information), and Manner (short and to-the-point communication). To generate a spooky impression, she makes up a ghost story, elaborates excessively, adds unimportant details, and employs theatrical language. Framton Nuttel misunderstands Vera's speech because he assumes she follows the maxims. He takes her word for it, interprets her explanations as relevant background, and ignores the dramatic cues. The story's comedy is fueled by this misinterpretation. The narrative may be a subtly critical look at Victorian communication practices that prioritized manners above bluntness. Vera's long story may be a satire on this kind of evasiveness, spinning a fanciful tale rather than inquiring about Nuttel's condition straight out. Nuttel's literal reading may be interpreted as a critique of those who don't understand the underlying meaning and take excessively flowery words at their value. Vera's ability to manipulate rests on Nuttel's conviction that she is abiding by the maxims. She tricks him by making up a tale that plays on his fears of ghosts and a serene getaway. Because of his social anxiety, Nuttel misinterprets social cues and is extremely sensitive to possible dangers. By examining Grice's maxims, we may better comprehend the comedy that results from miscommunication caused by expectations that aren't met. It clarifies the dangers of indirectness as well as possible societal criticism of Victorian communication techniques. We learn more about the motivations of the characters and how manipulation preys on fears and presumptions. In general, analyzing Grice's maxims deepens our comprehension of the comedy, social satire, and intricate character relationships in the novel. It emphasizes how crucial it is to communicate clearly and how, when expectations aren't met, there may be comedy and manipulation involved.

By showing how seemingly cooperative communication may result in comedy and manipulation due to flouted maxims, a pragmatic analysis of Grice's maxims in Munro's "The Open Window" makes a valuable contribution to the area of pragmatic analysis in literature. Nuttel, who follows the expected cooperation norms, misinterprets Vera's infractions of Quality (truth), Quantity (information overload), Relation (irrelevance), and Manner (dramatic exaggeration). This study enriches literary interpretations by highlighting the significance of taking assumptions, context, and purpose into account when interpreting communication. Munro (2023). Through the lens of Grice's maxims, this pragmatic analysis of "The Open Window" exposes an intriguing interaction between comedy and communication. Based on Nuttel's presumptions of cooperative communication, Vera produces a funny misunderstanding by playfully disregarding the maxims, especially honesty and relevance. The narrative raises the possibility of criticizing Victorian communication methods that were unduly indirect. Furthermore, by making use of Nuttel's fears, Vera investigates issues of social anxiety and manipulation. In the end, this realistic approach deepens our comprehension of the comedy, social criticism, and motivations of the characters in the novel. It emphasizes how crucial it is to communicate well and how expectations might be broken, leading to misunderstandings.

REFERENCES

1. Abba, A. G., Alhaji, M. G., Sanusi, H. A., & Ahmed, B. M. (2022). Contributions of the Gricean maxims in the understanding of meaning: A review. *Yamtara-Wala Journal of Arts, Management and Social Sciences (YaJAMSS)*, 2(2), 358-367. <https://yajamss.com.ng/index.php/yajamss/article/view/67>
2. Andy, A., & Ambalegin, A. (2019). Maxims violation on "Night at the Museum" movie. *Journal Basis*, 6(2), 215-224. <http://dx.doi.org/10.33884/basisupb.v6i2.1421>
3. Dewi, P. A. M. (2023). Conversational maxim violation by the characters in "Shang-Chi and the Legend of the Ten Rings" movie. *Lexicon*, 10(1), 31-38. <https://doi.org/10.22146/lexicon.v10i1.77798>
4. Eragamreddy, E. (2022). A semantic study of implicatures. *ELC Research Gate*, 3, 41-51.
5. Fonseka, E. G. (2015). Wickedness in the guise of courtesy: A critical reading of 'The Open Window' by H.H. Munro alias Saki. *Literary Quest*, 1(8), 16-29. https://www.academia.edu/download/36630108/Saki_-_The_Open_Window.pdf
6. Grice, H. P. (1975). Logic and conversation. In P. Cole & J. Morgan (Eds) *Syntax and Semantics, Vol. 3, Speech Acts* (pp. 41-58). Academic Press. <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/ls/studypacks/Grice-Logic.pdf>
7. Hossain, M. M. (2021). The application of Grice maxims in conversation: A pragmatic study. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 3(10), 32-40. <https://doi.org/10.32996/jeltal.2021.3.10.4>
8. Lalić, E. L. (2020). *Grice's Theory of Implicature* [Doctoral dissertation]. University of Rijeka.
9. Lavia, L., Witchel, H. J., Aletta, F., Steffens, J., Fiebig, A., Kang, J., ... & Healey, P. G. (2018). Non-participant observation methods for soundscape design and urban planning. In *Handbook of research on perception-driven approaches to urban assessment and design* (pp. 73-99). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-3637-6.ch004>

10. Maeedi, S. A., & Jasim, M. H. (2021). Investigating linguistic strategies of persuasion in “The Open Window” by Saki with specific reference to Johnstone’s Model: A stylistic study. *Adab Al-Basrah*, 97(2), 20-39. <https://www.iasj.net/iasj/article/218778>
11. Munro, H. H. (2023). *The collected short stories of Saki*. Rustam Prakashan.
12. Putra, I. G. K. A., Maharani, P. D., & Hikmaharyanti, P. D. A. (2023). Context situation analysis of characters’ utterance in “Little” movie: Maxim of quality violation. *ELYSIAN JOURNAL: English Literature, Linguistics and Translation Studies*, 3(1), 144-156.
13. Rahmi, S. S., Refnaldi, R., & Wahyuni, D. (2018). The violation of conversational maxims found in political conversation at Rosi Talkshow. *English Language and Literature*, 7(1), 177-183.
14. Safonova, M. A. (2013). Concerning the stylistic peculiarities of HH Munro's short stories. *Bulletin of Perm University. Russian and foreign philology*, 3, 114-119.
15. Saki. (2017). *The chronicles of Clovis* (1912). Create Space Independent Publishing Platform.
16. Singh, R. (2022). Deconstructing HH Munro Saki's 'The Open Window': A critical study. *Research Review International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 7(4), 109-114. <https://doi.org/10.31305/rrijm.2022.v07.i04.016>
17. Stanley, M. (2014). Qualitative descriptive: A very good place to start. In S. Nayar., & M. Stanley (Eds) *Qualitative research methodologies for occupational science and therapy* (pp. 21-36). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203383216>
18. Tannen, D., Hamilton, H. E., & Schiffrin, D. (2015). *The handbook of discourse analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.
19. Wilson, D., & Sperber, D. (2022). On Grice's theory of conversation. In Paul Werth (Eds) *Conversation and discourse* (pp. 155-178). Routledge. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4324/9781003291039-11>
20. Yuldasheva, F. (2024). Gricean maxims of conversational cooperation. *Models and Methods in Modern Science*, 3(3), 57-61. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10774967>